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INTRODUCTION

SENS sensor is designed for **real-time acoustic monitoring**, currently dedicated to **urban soundscapes**. Built on a **Raspberry Pi Model 4B** with a USB-connected microphone, SENS captures sound continuously and processes it locally (to **safeguard privacy**) using custom-developed software based on **small and efficient AI** algorithms. SENS calculates acoustic parameters (**Leq** and **LAeq**), and makes predictions of the perceptual sound attributes of **pleasantness and eventfulness** (ISO 12913), along with detecting the presence of specific **sound sources**. Additionally, the system transmits the audio interpretation to a remote server, using **mobile data connectivity**.

STRUCTURE

HANDLING COMPUTATIONAL LIMITATIONS

When SENS boots up, all machine learning models (CLAP and individual source detection models) load before starting normal operation. The graph shows the device's memory usage for different configurations, highlighting that a simplified CLAP model (which only includes the audio encoder), and the use of PCA for reducing embeddings' dimensionality, improves efficiency and prevents crashes or freezes.

SENS IN REAL LIFE

SENS monitoring and interpretation of a synthetic but realistic urban soundscape, with the plot background color representing emotional perception: red or green for pleasantness, and color intensity for eventfulness (instantaneous parameters). Predictions for sound sources are displayed on top. The graph shows the active sources and their resulting perception over time.

CONCLUSIONS

SENS represents an innovative step in environmental noise monitoring, offering real-time processing and robust privacy protection. A single SENS device, or a network of them, can serve as a powerful tool for understanding the acoustic characteristics of soundscapes with efficiency and flexibility.